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pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

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THE EFFECTS OF READINESS - REINFORCEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL AND MANIPULATIVE MATERIALS IN ACQUIRING THE DIVERSE NEEDS OF STUDENTS IN SPECIAL NEEDS EDUCATION AS PERCEIVED BY SNED TEACHERS IN LAUREL SUB-OFFICE FOR S.Y. 2022-2023

JAY-AR A. TENORIO, MAEd

*Special Education Teacher I
Balakilong Integrated School
Division Of Batangas Province*

This study aimed to discover and understand how significant reinforcement of educational and manipulative materials to the diverse needs of students in special needs education. A descriptive research design was employed in this study. Participants were chosen using purposive sampling strategy with four SNED Teachers from public schools within Laurel Sub-Office in SDO-Batangas Province, namely; Bugaan Integrated School, Laurel Central School, Molinete Elementary School and Wenceslao Trinidad Memorial National High School. The research instruments used in this study were the self-made online questionnaire through google form and one-on-one follow-up interviews. Findings of this study revealed that all SNED teacher respondents agreed that reinforcing manipulative and educational materials is a huge help to develop, acquire, assist and facilitate SNED Teachers in transmitting, organizing knowledge, skills, and attitude to the learners with disabilities within an instructional situation. On one hand, most SNED teachers also agreed that providing specialized resources and materials to support SNED teachers not only improved their ability to meet the unique requirements of learners with disabilities but also fostered a more inclusive and engaging learning environment. Moreover, recognizing the importance of teacher training in Special Needs Education is crucial to provide ongoing professional development opportunities for SNED teachers. These opportunities should focus on equipping educators with the skills and knowledge necessary to effectively use the manipulative and educational materials and adapt instruction to meet diverse needs of learners with disabilities.

Insights from this research are valuable for informing policy development and advocacy efforts. By focusing on the socioeconomic and psychological challenges faced by school nurses, stakeholders can develop strategies to support these essential professionals better. This, in turn, can positively impact the health and wellbeing of both students and the broader community in Central Luzon.

Overall, the study provides a thorough understanding of the factors influencing the psychological wellbeing of school nurses, offering a foundation for future improvements in the field.

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